

Humans can clone animals by manipulating its genetic material to make another animal that is quite identical to the original animal. Animal cloning can be useful but it can also be very unethical. In today's article I will be diving into the world of animal cloning and figuring out whether it is ethical to clone animals or not.

Let's start by talking about the big benefit of cloning animals. Animal cloning can be used to bring back species on the brink of extinction. A popular example of this would be the case of the black footed ferrets. The scientists cloned the black footed ferret named Elizabeth Ann in December of 2020. This sparked hope for the conservation of the species. There are currently around 350 black footed ferrets in the wild. This is a prime example about how cloning animals can be beneficial.

While the ability to bring back species on the brink of extinction is amazing there are also many cons to cloning such as animal welfare being jeopardized. For example cloned sheep, cows, and mice have been known to die shortly after birth. For example a cloned two month old calf passed away after developing blood and heart problems. These animals suffer and die at a young age. In fact 96 percent of cloned animals do not make it past 6 months of age.

In conclusion we should only use cloning as a last resort to save a species due to the high mortality rate of cloned animals and possible long term effects that could hinder an animal's ability to live as it was meant to.

Citations

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